

D8.4: Healthy Cities Helix

VARCITIES | Work Package 8, Task 8.5

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Article 29.5 Disclaimer

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Executive Summary

This report is part of the Task 8.5 Healthy Cities Helix and Clustering with Relevant Projects, within Work Package 8: Exploitation and business models.

This report details the steps of the creation of the Healthy Cities Helix and its management. It outlines a strategy that the Crowdhelix team will implement in order to grow and maintain the community, as well as bringing the project's technology closer to market.

This report also includes annexes to help the partners get familiar with this part of VARCITIES's dissemination activities, and to offer additional context to those who are not yet familiar with the Crowdhelix platform.

Further updates on the development of the Healthy Cities Helix and reports regarding the 4 annual helix stakeholder events will be included in the periodic management reports.

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Abbreviation List

Term	Description
H&WB	Health and well-being
D	Deliverable
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020
IT	Information Technology
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
VARCITIES	Visionary Nature Based Actions For Health, Wellbeing & Resilience In Cities

Introduction

For European-funded projects, enhancing their impact and ensuring their sustainability is a crucial issue. The new Healthy Cities Helix is calibrated to support VARCITIES through its various development stages, including post-project. The Crowdhelix Open Innovation platform will notably provide access to domain experts, SMEs & industry partners, as well as strategic links to commercial accelerators.

The Crowdhelix platform facilitates connections between various types of stakeholders sharing common interests via the opportunities posted under up to three themed Helixes. Interested parties can contact the author via public or private messages. The platform users can also engage proactively by using the search tool - which is refined by opportunities (posts), organisations, groups ("sub-organisations"), or experts (users) - to contact potential partners directly.

Crowdhelix, either via face-to-face meetings or online via its platform, has facilitated numerous successful collaborations. The Norges Teknisk-Naturvitenskapelige Universitet (NTNU) from Norway submitted a Horizon 2020 proposal following Crowdhelix event introductions. EBOS, a Cyprus-based SME, was introduced to a Spanish SME via the platform, and they are now collaborating on two newly-funded projects.

Deliverable Overview and Structure

Section 2 provides background information about the Crowdhelix platform, on which the Healthy Cities Helix is hosted. It also addresses the main objectives of the community and terminology used in the report to describe the workings of the platform and of the Helix. In section 3, the process of creating the bespoke Healthy Cities Helix has been presented. This includes the process the Crowdhelix team follows to onboard the project partners to the Crowdhelix platform. Section 4 outlines the strategy Crowdhelix will implement to expand the cluster and build a strong community of experts in smart cities, H&WB, climate and nature-based solutions integrating digital, societal and cultural innovation. Finally, Annex I is a guide designed to help the partners set up their organisational and personal profiles on the Crowdhelix platform, and Annex II is a statement of membership, which the VARCITIES partners need to sign in order to join the Crowdhelix Network.

Background

Crowdhelix is a pan-European Open Innovation Network that connects and enables research organisations, SMEs and industry to collaborate, innovate and grow. The Network has more than 400+ member organisations from 45 countries and is present in all EU Member State countries.

The Network is set-up around thematic areas (called “Helixes”), e.g. Health Helix, Societies Helix, and Digital Helix etc., and is supported by a technology platform (<https://www.crowdhelix.com/>), where these virtual communities are hosted.

A Helix is a specialised community/cluster comprising experts and research and innovation professionals across academia and industry. The Crowdhelix platform consists of multiple thematic helixes, whose reach extends to 400,000+ research and innovation actors (across its members), and directly to 4,000+ users currently on the Crowdhelix platform. It provides its members with the following main functionalities:

- Announcements
- Collaboration opportunities posting
- Expertise offer
- Search engine for identifying suitable collaborators
- Interaction with experts/organisations

A **Healthy Cities Helix** (<https://crowdhelix.com/helixes/healthy-cities>) has been created within the framework of the VARCITIES project. It will accelerate the project’s dissemination, communication and commercialisation strategies, in order to build a strong, self-sustaining community of like-minded stakeholders that will have access to updates on the project and collaborate with experts in their field of interest.

Crowdhelix is a membership based platform, meaning that in order to access the full capacity of the platform, i.e. all functions detailed above, dedicated account manager, access to network events and all the Helixes (some 40 communities) members pay a yearly fee. Membership is open to Organisations and not individuals. Individuals can join clusters (Helixes) relevant to their expertise regardless of their organisation, but their ability to engage depends on the organisation being or not being a member, as it will be further described in section 4. The membership fee depends on the type and size of an organisation in order to offer all interested organisations the possibility to join the platform and the network. For example, fees for SMEs are much lower than that for universities, research centres and multinational corporations.

VARCITIES Project partners, researchers and stakeholders have free access to the Healthy Cities Helix. The same has been extended to funded sister projects. Crowdhelix will maintain the Healthy Cities Helix and it will remain active for at least 2 years after the end of the VARCITIES project. At

the end of the 2 year period, after the project has ended, individual experts will be invited to keep their account for free. Should organisations wish to have full access to the platform after the end of the project, then they can enquire about membership.

Main Objectives and Goals

The Healthy Cities Helix will play a key role in the project's dissemination activities by creating and building a pool of stakeholders, who will be informed about the project's development. Some of them will be significantly involved in the commercial exploitation process.

The goal is to have 150 organisations profiled on the Healthy Cities Helix by the end of M12. They will include end-users, exploiters, participants of previously funded Horizon 2020 projects and other relevant industrial actors. This variety of stakeholders will cover all the project's aspects, and will therefore guarantee continued interest from key actors, during and after the project.

Terminology

Crowdhelix platform - Online Open Innovation platform run by Crowdhelix Limited that facilitates collaboration and supports project impact across an international network of universities, research organisations, companies, and Horizon 2020 actions.

Dissemination - The act of sharing research results with potential users - peers in the research field, industry, other commercial players and policymakers.

Helix - An online technology cluster/community of actors sharing an interest in a specific topic. Themed Helixes, such as Healthy Cities Helix, are hosted on the Crowdhelix platform.

Stakeholder - A person with an interest or concern in something, in this case societal sciences and humanities, architecture, design studies, urban planning, big data, H&WB, climate and nature-based solutions.

Healthy Cities – smart cities focused on H&WB, climate and nature-based solutions integrating digital, societal and cultural innovation.

Creation of the Healthy Cities Helix

Crowdhelix started the process of creating the Healthy Cities Helix with designing a logo that reflects the focus of the community: ecosystems that are stable now and sustainable in the long term, and aligning the related Helixes to complement the Healthy Cities one (Fig.1.). The Healthy Cities Helix became active in Month 2 (12th October 2020) to all organisations on the Crowdhelix platform. All future members of the platform will be prompted to sign up for the Healthy Cities Helix.

Figure 1 Helix logos designs

Following the launch of the Helix, Crowdhelix began inviting all project partners to join the Network and create a profile on the platform (partner organisations and individuals), in order to join the Healthy Cities Helix. This Helix was created specifically for the VARCITIES Project and will grow to include a wide range of expertise from organisations and businesses with a focus on societal sciences, humanities, architecture, urban planning, big data, H&WB, and climate. The team proceeded as follows:

- Project partners were sent the membership agreement (terms and conditions) sent to all members of Crowdhelix. Upon receipt of a signed copy of this agreement, project partners were sent an invitation to sign up to the platform.
- Once on board, each partner was assigned a main administrator with the power to build their organisation's profile, invite colleagues to access the platform and start using the platform as a networking and collaboration tool.

- Upon onboarding on the platform, each partner gets assigned an account manager/ a main point of contact for helping with any platform related inquiry that they might have. Crowdhelix staff remain at their disposal for advice, matchmaking and dissemination whenever needed for the duration of the project

- As previously mentioned, Crowdhelix is a membership based platform and full members pay a yearly fee depending on the size and type of organisations. As part of the project, VARCITIES partners can utilise the platform as members, free of charge during the lifetime of the project.

- With the intent of expanding the Healthy Cities Helix community, the Crowdhelix team is using their existing network and knowledge to identify potential stakeholders. The platform has an existing pool of 4,500+ users, out of which 2075 were automatically notified about the launch of the helix (Fig. 2). All Crowdhelix users have access to all the posts, including the Healthy Cities posts. Additionally, the launch of the Helix was communicated to the users of the platform in a dedicated post (Fig. 3).

The Crowdhelix Development Team is also working on the Healthy Cities Helix page (Fig. 5) in order to make it more appealing, add a sense of community and add extra space to the content related to VARCITIES.

New Healthy Cities Helix

We are pleased to announce the launch of the Healthy Cities Helix, an international Open Innovation community of specialists in the fields of environment, smart cities, architecture, and related disciplines. This Helix has been launched as a focus for impact and dissemination services in support of the VARCITIES project's ambition to contribute to the shaping of future cities, by designing and developing nature-based solutions (NBS). The VARCITIES project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869505.

[Healthy Cities Helix](#)

Figure 2 Healthy Cities Helix Announcement

Andreea Petrea
for **CrowdHelix**
10 days ago in **Healthy Cities**

Send Message

Invitation to join the Healthy Cities Helix

Seeking expertise:

- Nature-based solutions
- Health & wellbeing
- Healthy cities
- Resilient cities
- Human centred cities

♥ 12

Dear CrowdHelix members,

We are pleased to invite you to join the new 'Healthy City Helix' community. This Helix arises from a newly funded Horizon 2020 innovation action called VARCITIES*.

The vision of VARCITIES is to implement real, visionary ideas and add value by establishing sustainable models for increasing health and wellbeing of citizens.

The Healthy Cities Helix will form the hub of a virtual community where you can collaborate with your peers and will be able to follow the project's advancements, activities, events, and results. Within the Helix you can share and join specific collaboration opportunities related to this topic. You can also invite any stakeholders outside of the Network who may be interested in this field, and whom you trust to participate.

To join the Healthy City Helix visit <https://crowdHelix.com/helixes/healthy-cities> and click "Follow". You will then be notified of new opportunities posted, according to your chosen notification settings.

*The VARCITIES project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869505

Figure 3 Invitation for platform users to join the Healthy Cities Helix

Figure 4 Current Helixes on the Crowdhelix Platform

Healthy Cities Unfollow

Visionary nature based solutions for human centered cities. Sustainable transition to smart & future cities

Background

In an increasingly urbanising world, governments and international corporations strive to increase productivity of cities, recognized as economic growth hubs, as well as ensuring better quality of life and living conditions to citizens. Although significant effort is performed by international organisations, researchers, etc. to transform the challenges of cities into opportunities, the visions of our urban future are trending towards bleak. Social services and health facilities are significantly affected in negative ways owed to the increase in urban populations (70% by 2050). Air pollution and urban exacerbation of heat islands is exacerbating. Nature will struggle to compensate in the future city, as rural land is predicted to shrink by 30% affecting liveability.

Key project: VARCITIES

VARCITIES puts the citizen and the "human community" in the eye of the future cities' vision. Future cities should evolve to be human centred cities. The vision of VARCITIES is to implement real, visionary ideas and add value by establishing sustainable models for increasing health and wellbeing of citizens (children, young people, middle age, elderly) that are exposed to diverse climatic conditions and challenges around Europe through shared public spaces that make cities liveable and welcoming.

The Healthy Cities Helix is an international Open Innovation community of specialists in the fields of environment, smart cities, architecture, and related disciplines. The Helix was launched as a focus for impact and dissemination services in support of the VARCITIES project's ambition to contribute to the shaping of future cities by designing and developing nature-based (NBS) solutions.

The VARCITIES project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869505

Andrea Petrea
Helix Manager

Message

Denia Kolokotsa
Helix Leader

Projects

VARCITIES
Key Project

Resources

EU Publication: "The Human Centred City"

Latest Opportunities

Figure 5 Current look of the Healthy Cities Helix page

Community expansion

Once the Healthy Cities Helix has been launched and the partners have been onboarded to the platform, the Crowdhelix team will start working on reaching experts beyond Crowdhelix members and build a strong community around the Helix.

In order to open the Helix community free of charge to stakeholders outside the Crowdhelix platform and to also insure the quality of posts and engagement on the platform individuals from outside the Crowdhelix Network interested in joining the community, will be granted limited access to the platform. This means that they will not be able to directly post their own collaboration opportunities but they will have access to those published by others. They will also have access to any communication and dissemination materials for VARCITIES as part of the resource section or the announcement block. Additionally, they can leave comments to express their interest in specific opportunities, but those comments will have to be approved by the Crowdhelix team as the Crowdhelix platform is a curated platform and, therefore, the team ensures that the relevant opportunities are published and the platform is not misused for other purposes. Figure 6 below explains the different types of access available for different stakeholders.

		View Helix descriptions and Public Posts	View and respond to all posts, including private	Post Opportunities	Org account management	Who?
1	Not registered - visitor	✓	✗	✗	✗	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interested public Future stakeholders/ subscribers
2	Trusted Collaborator & Sister Projects &	✓	✓	✗	✗	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Key invited stakeholders Sister project partners
3	Project Partners	✓	✓	✓	For Project Helix	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All project partners, associated partners
3	Standard Subscriber	✓	✓	✓	Across all helixes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All Crowdhelix members interested in opportunities across the R&I spectrum

Figure 6 Types of access on the Crowdhelix platform

The Crowdhelix team will focus on extending the Healthy Cities community by reaching out to existing funded projects under the same topic, as well as other funded Horizon 2020 projects in this space. These projects will be invited to join the Helix as a way to learn more about VARCITIES's results and build a virtual community/marketplace of like-minded stakeholders/end-users, which will support accelerating the exploitation of VARCITIES's results and help achieve its post-project impact objectives.

Crowdhelix together with the rest of the VARCITIES partners from WP8 will also reach out to research and innovation actors that are not yet members of the Network to join the Helix.

Organisations (including sector-specific networks, associations and foundations), that the consortium partners would like to engage with, will be also discussed in WP4. A list will be compiled as part of D4.1 Local Stakeholder mapping report and integrated into the Helix Strategy, and Crowdhelix will begin reaching out to these organisations. Additionally, a link to the Healthy Cities Helix will be available on the VARCITIES website, where relevant experts will be encouraged to get in touch with the Crowdhelix team should they wish to join the Helix.

As the Helix is a community dedicated to experts and researchers interested in Nature-Based Solution and smart cities and is a targeted tool, the main promotional vehicle for the Helix will be events: both organised by the project as well as events in which partners are involved in. As social media targets the general public, these accounts will only be used to promote the Helix community only in special circumstances where the posts are more targeted towards researchers and not the general public. This is to ensure that only relevant stakeholders are invited into the community, ensuring the relevance of its opportunities and its long term impact. The Helix Manager will ensure the consortium partners are aware of the latest developments on the platform. They will be encouraged to use their own network to promote the Helix to potential stakeholders, contributing to the community's growth.

The first Helix Event will be held by the end of Year 1 and will be discussed with the rest of the partners. This will be an opportunity to approach more potential community members. Design of this event will be informed both by the desire to cross-feed more general project dissemination activities (publication of news, views, project public deliverables) with the activities of the Helix and to engage with and link up with a full range of stakeholder bodies and individuals. Announcements related to the first Helix meeting will be issued on the platform and through VARCITIES's broader channels (website, social media accounts). The event follow-up will be facilitated through the platform - which will be an incentive for the attendees to join Crowdhelix to continue the collaboration.

Commercial exploitation

The Healthy Cities Helix will serve as a hub throughout and after the project. As the community grows, the potential for the project's output to enter the market will be greater. The Crowdhelix team will reach out to the pool of platform users that are in a position to help accelerate the product's commercialisation phase once credible outcomes can be shared. Additionally, they, with the support of the consortium partners, will leverage all relevant networks.

Crowdhelix will work closely with Inlecom to identify relevant actors that could be willing to invest in the product. The online community will serve as a basis to facilitate connections with key industrial actors to pave the way for exploiting the project's results.

CONCLUSION

The Healthy Cities Helix is now active and has already reached out to 2,000+ users of the platform. The metrics are being continually improved to better gauge Crowdhelix users' interest and participation in this particular community, which will allow the Helix Manager and team to accelerate the community more effectively. The Crowdhelix development team will therefore make tools available to better grasp the number of potential stakeholders for the community. With regards to the Crowdhelix project management team, they will use different channels to contact and encourage experts in smart cities, H&WB, climate and nature-based solutions to join the community.

Annex I: Crowdhelix - a guide to the platform

Signing up

In order to join the platform, you must either be a member of the network or be invited by a Crowdhelix user who considers you as a trusted collaborator. For the second option, you will

Figure 7 Example of invitation (1)

receive an invitation email from a current member (Fig. 7 and Fig 8).

Figure 8 Example of invitation (2)

By clicking on the sign up link, you will be directed to fill out a short form (Fig. 9). In order for your request to be automatically accepted, please select your organisation and use an email address with the corresponding domain. If you are unable to find your organisation on the list, please contact hello@crowdhelix.com. The Crowdhelix Team will then be in touch with the guidelines for signing up to the platform.

Create your account

If you are an employee or student at an organisation participating in the [CrowdHelix Network](#) you can create a CrowdHelix account for free.

If not, and you would like to discuss membership for your organisation, please [contact us](#).

Email Please use your organisation address

Password

First name

Last name

Organisation

I agree to the [Terms of Service](#) and confirm that I have read the [Privacy Policy](#).

Sign up

Already have an account? [Sign in](#)

Open Collaboration

Join a global research & innovation community of over 2290+ active experts.

Anna Harrold
University of Leeds

Our Chair in Robotics and Autonomous Systems at the University of Leeds is very interested in participating in a bid for this call. If you could let me know a few more details about the proposed project I would be very happy to put you in touch with him.

Write a response...

Figure 9 Form to create an account

Completing your personal profile

Once you have reached the main page, click on the drop-down arrow next to your name at the top right corner of the screen. Next, choose Profile settings. Next, you will be asked to fill in your Job Title, Expertise and Interest Keywords (Fig. 10). This will help us to properly profile you on the platform, and will increase the possibility of you being contacted by other members of the platform seeking your expertise. Uploading your profile photo is a nice final touch and builds trust within the network between members.

100%

Profile details

First Name: Andreea | Last Name: Petrea

Job Title: Communication & Events Manager

Link to your professional profile: e.g. <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/ResearchGa>

[Change email](#) | [Change password](#) | [Send a Personal Data Request](#)

Organisations

Crowdhelix | Confirmed | Leave

[+ Join another organisation...](#)

Groups

Community & Project Management Team | Leave

Expertise

Expertise Keywords: Horizon 2020, matchmaking, Outreach Events, Events management

Interest Keywords: Communication, Cultural Heritage

Figure 10 Example of profile settings

Once your profile is complete, click on Notifications (below Account settings). Here, you are able to set different email notification settings for each Helix (Fig. 10). For example, if you are only interested in opportunities in “Healthy Cities,” you can unsubscribe from all of the other Helixes and stop receiving emails completely, or receive only daily or weekly “digest” email notifications about them.

☑ Notification preferences

Pick your topics of interest:

How would you like to be notified?

Opportunities posted in your topics of interest Instant	▼
Opportunities posted in other topics Weekly	▼
Private message notifications Yes	▼
Alert me of new comments on my posts Yes	▼
Receive post recommendations from other users Yes	▼

Update

Figure 11 Example of notifications settings

Updating your organisation’s profile

From the menu at the top right of the screen, select Your organisation’s name under Manage Organisations. From there, we would advise you to add your organisation’s logo and description, as well as a few keywords on your expertise (Fig. 12). This profile will be the first impression the users will have of your organisation, and should therefore reflect its strengths and fields of interest. Don’t be afraid to brag a bit about your track record, this also builds trust between members!

Figure 12 Example of organisation dashboard

Adding groups, administrators and users

Once your organization's profile is complete (Fig. 13), you can invite your colleagues by clicking on Invite User at the right side of your screen. As the Organization's Leader, you have the right to appoint administrators who can co-manage your organizations' profile. This can be easily done via the Dashboard; you can click on your colleagues' name to promote them.

You may structure your organisation into groups (e.g. corresponding to a university department). Each group can have one leader and multiple managers. In order to set up a group, please click on "Create group" at the top right of the organisation dashboard (Fig. 14).

The screenshot shows the Crowdhelix organization profile. At the top, there is a header with the organization's logo, name, address (85 Great Portland Street, First Floor, London, GB), and website (http://www.crowdhelix.com). Below this, the 'About' section provides a description of Crowdhelix as an Open Innovation platform connecting universities, research organizations, and companies. It mentions funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe programs. The 'Expertise' section lists 'innovation', 'Collaboration', 'research', and 'open innovation'. On the right side, the 'Leader details' section features a profile for Abdul Rahim, Co-founder and Director (UK), with a contact number (+442076872020) and a 'Send message' button. Below this, the 'Groups' section lists three teams: 'Community & Project Management Team', 'Development Team', and 'Founders'. At the bottom right, the 'Helixes' section shows a row of icons representing different organizational structures or projects.

Figure 13 Example of organisation's profile

Search Crowdhelix

Opportunities Helixes Network Contact

Crowdhelix
Organisation Dashboard
[View Profile](#)

Organisation details

[Change photo](#)

Name
Crowdhelix

Street
85 Great Portland Street, First Floor

City
London

Organisation groups

- Community & Project Management Team [Manage](#)
- Development Team [Manage](#)
- Founders [Manage](#)
- [+ Create group](#)

Organisation members (18)

[learn more about promoting & account types](#)

Riam Kansa	riam@crowdhelix.com	Manage
Rusty Nash	rusty@rustynash.co.uk	Manage
Martin Scott (Admin)	martin@crowdhelix.com	
Ryan Holder (Admin)	rholder101@gmail.com	
Kimberly Cornfield	kimberly.cornfield@crowdhelix.com	Manage
Abdul Rahim	abdul@crowdhelix.com	

Figure 14 Creating and managing a group

Posting a collaboration opportunity (only for members of the network)

You are now ready to post your first collaborative opportunity! To do so, go to the Crowdfelix homepage/Helix and click 'New Post' at the right of your screen. Ideally, opportunities should be open to organisations from any country, and are usually related to some form of funding. They can be posted in up to three "Helixes," which are categorical labels that describe the general theme of your opportunity. You can also specify if you are looking for a specific type of organisation to work with (SME, research centre/university, corporation or expert) (Fig 15).

*** Opportunity title**

e.g. Seeking international collaborators for upcoming Digital Health call

Are you targeting a Horizon 2020 call?
If so, use the box below to search for the call, using either the title or the identification code.

e.g. ICT-38-2020

Who are you posting on behalf of?
Choose your organisation and (if applicable) your department / research group.

Organisation*

Select Organisation

*** Which Helix communities are relevant to your opportunity?**
Choose up to three Helixes to share your opportunity in.

+ Add Helix

*** Which roles would you be willing to take in the collaboration?**
Select all that apply

Coordinator Work Package Leader
Consortium Partner Individual Expert

What expertise from potential collaborators would help you target this opportunity?

e.g. Big data, Statistics, Robotics...

Press enter after each keyword

*** Describe your collaboration opportunity**

For best results, please specify what you hope to achieve from the collaboration (e.g. a project proposal) and be clear about what expertise you're seeking, so that potential collaborators know whether they're suitable.

This will also mean that Crowdfelix's intelligent recommender system will be better able to match your opportunity with appropriate collaborators.

How widely can your opportunity be shared?
Control who can see it, and whether other users can share it with their trusted collaborators outside the Crowdfelix Network.

Visibility

 Extended Network
Visible to network members and their trusted collaborators

Figure 15 Example of collaboration opportunity posting

Some pieces of advice:

- Keep the title short and concise
- Tags are a key element to determine the user's interest
- We would recommend that you set the visibility to Extended network. This will maximise your chances of finding the perfect fit, while also targeting trusted collaborators.

Bear in mind that the Crowdhelix Team will review and moderate your post before going live, and we will get back to you with suggested updates if needed.

Interacting with the Community

Via the Opportunities posted

- You can contact a post's author by commenting below the opportunity or sending them a private message (Fig 16).
- You can grant limited access to Crowdhelix to a trusted collaborator that is not yet registered by clicking on the **Share this opportunity** below the post (Fig. 16).

Andreea Petrea
for Crowdfunder
a month ago in Healthy Cities

Invitation to join the Healthy Cities Helix

Seeking expertise:

Nature-based solutions Health & wellbeing Healthy cities Resilient cities Human centred cities

Dear Crowdfunder members,

We are pleased to invite you to join the new 'Healthy City Helix' community. This Helix arises from a newly funded Horizon 2020 innovation action called VARCITIES*.

The vision of VARCITIES is to implement real, visionary ideas and add value by establishing sustainable models for increasing health and wellbeing of citizens.

The Healthy Cities Helix will form the hub of a virtual community where you can collaborate with your peers and will be able to follow the project's advancements, activities, events, and results. Within the Helix you can share and join specific collaboration opportunities related to this topic. You can also invite any stakeholders outside of the Network who may be interested in this field, and whom you trust to participate.

To join the Healthy City Helix visit <https://crowdfunder.com/helixes/healthy-cities> and click "Follow". You will then be notified of new opportunities posted, according to your chosen notification settings.

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Know a potential collaborator for this opportunity?
Andreea wants to find the best possible collaborator worldwide for this opportunity, and so has opened it to individuals from outside the Crowdfunder Network.

Send Message

Share this opportunity

Responses

Write a response...

Figure 16 Interacting with the community via the opportunities posted

Via the Search Tool

- At the top of the main page, you can search either for posts, experts, and organisations by name or by keyword (Fig 17).

Figure 17 The search tool

- You can send private messages to other users by clicking the **Send Message** button on their profile (Fig 18). If you want to contact an organisation, you can find its main contact person (**Leader**) on the organisation’s profile (Fig. 18).

Figure 18 Sending private messages from a member's profile

Figure 19 Contacting an organisation

Anything unclear?

We're always very happy to help! Just email hello@crowdhelix.com.

Annex II: Statement of membership for VARCITIES partners

Crowdhelix

Open Innovation Network

Statement of Membership

Example Membership Agreement

Summary

The Crowdhelix Network is an international Open Innovation platform for research organisations & companies participating in the 'Horizon 2020' EU funding programme, and intending to participate in its successor programme 'Horizon Europe'. It facilitates connections between leading research institutions and innovating businesses around the world, so that together they can target such programmes with a view to delivering pioneering collaborative projects. The Crowdhelix Network is powered by the custom-built online collaboration platform "[Crowdhelix](#)". Crowdhelix Limited hereby offers its services on a subscription basis to Example Membership Agreement , in accordance with the terms of the below Membership Agreement.

Member Details

Member Organisation

Example Membership Agreement

Membership Number

Member Address

Initial Membership Period

(date of receiving the membership statement) to 28/02/2025

Membership Fee

€0

Primary Contact

Email:
Phone:

The Crowdhelix Network Details

Company Information

Crowdhelix Limited, trading as The Crowdhelix Network ("Crowdhelix")
 85 Great Portland Street, First Floor, London, W1W 7LT, United Kingdom
 Crowdhelix Limited is a company registered in England & Wales
 Company Registration Number: 8336338
 Company VAT Number: GB 185 4751 77

Primary Contact

Abdul Rahim
 Director
 Crowdhelix Limited
 Email: abdul@crowdhelix.com
 Phone: +44 20 7687 2020

Additional Contacts

Membership Support: members@crowdhelix.com
 Technical Support: support@crowdhelix.com
 Payments & Invoicing: payments@crowdhelix.com

Membership Duration

Upon payment of the Membership Fee indicated above in accordance with the attached invoice, and upon execution of the Membership Agreement below, Example Membership Agreement shall be granted membership of The Crowdhelix Network from (date of receiving the membership statement) until 28/02/2025 (the 'Membership Period').

At the end of the Membership Period Example Membership Agreement may be invited by Crowdhelix to renew its membership. Any renewal of Example Membership Agreement 's membership shall be at the discretion of both parties. Crowdhelix may decide to offer Example Membership Agreement the opportunity to renew its membership either:

1. As an extension to the Membership Period indicated above, under the same terms as the below Membership Agreement. Such an extension shall enter into effect automatically upon payment of the relevant renewal invoice, or;

Under the terms of a revised Membership Agreement as proposed by Crowdhelix.

Membership Fee

The fee for the membership of Example Membership Agreement for the Membership Period is €0 (the 'Membership Fee'). Value Added Tax (VAT) shall be added to the Membership Fee where applicable, and the Membership Fee shall be paid by Example Membership Agreement to Crowdhelix in accordance with the terms of the enclosed invoice. Please contact payments@crowdhelix.com for invoicing and accounts queries.

Membership Benefits

The Crowdhelix Network is an international collaboration platform that endeavours to help organisations achieve their ambitions in the EU’s “Horizon 2020” research and innovation funding programme. A foundation of research intensive academic institutions is complemented by a core of corporate partners and SMEs, creating a novel cross-sector and international partnership structure for developing project consortia and networking activities.

Membership of The Crowdhelix Network is offered to Example Membership Agreement in order to help it to derive value from the Horizon 2020 funding programme, through the facilitation of consortium-building activities and through the provision of ready access to groups of excellent organisations that can offer complementary and targeted research and innovation expertise.

Crowdhelix hosts communities called "Helixes", which act as a focus for collaborations focused on a particular research area. Example Membership Agreement, once a member of Crowdhelix, may invite members of its staff to participate in any Helix and to act as a representative of Example Membership Agreement within the respective research area. Each Helix acts as a community for cross-sector networking activities, and can be used as a basis to form consortia and/or comment on the agenda of the European Commission as it develops its bi-annual Horizon 2020 Work Programmes.

Online collaboration is facilitated by the purpose-built [Crowdhelix](#) Open Innovation platform. An unlimited number of employees of Example Membership Agreement may sign up to Crowdhelix, in order to network with other participants, post appropriate opportunities to collaborate, and respond to opportunities posted by other users.

Each Helix also holds topic-focused events and acts as a cross-sector and international collaboration platform for launching successful Horizon 2020 proposals. Crowdhelix will hold at least one major event each year, bringing together members of the network and outside experts to provide training, information and insights regarding the Horizon 2020 funding programme, and/or its successor, ‘Horizon Europe’.

Smaller networking and strategy meetings will also be held on an *ad hoc* basis, focused on particular Helixes or on particular Horizon 2020 funding calls. Such events will be free to Example Membership Agreement, and up to three representatives of Example Membership Agreement may be invited to attend each event, depending upon the capacity and focus of the event.

As a member, Example Membership Agreement also has access to a specialist helpdesk service provided by Crowdhelix, through which a member of Crowdhelix staff will provide expert advice concerning:

1. Horizon 2020, its themes, calls and priorities;
2. The developing Horizon Europe funding programme;
3. Networking, consortium-building and partner search queries;
4. Queries concerning The Crowdhelix Network and its activities.

This helpdesk can be accessed directly by by their emailing the dedicated network members’ support desk at members@crowdhelix.com. All queries will be responded to either via email or telephone within three business days.

Email newsletters detailing Crowdhelix’s activities, events and updates will be sent to any staff member of Example Membership Agreement wishing to receive them, and subscriptions to this service can be arranged via <http://bit.ly/v2020net>

Crowdhelix’s group of “expert members” also provide access to bespoke training courses, innovation management expertise, and proposal and project management services within the network under negotiated rates. Access to the specialist services of Crowdhelix’s expert members can be organised at the institutional and the network level - contact the team for details.

The success of, and benefits that may be derived from, Example Membership Agreement’s participation in The Crowdhelix Network will depend upon the extent to which Example Membership Agreement and its staff are willing to engage in the platform and its activities. In this regard, Crowdhelix anticipates that particular Helixes will be more active and/or more effective than others, depending upon their composition, the current phase of the Horizon 2020 funding cycle, and the level of interest of participants in the respective research area.

Membership Agreement

This Membership Agreement shall be executed in one electronic original to indicate that this section (“Membership Agreement”) forms a legally binding Memorandum of Understanding between Example Membership Agreement and Crowdhelix Limited, the company implementing and administering The Crowdhelix Network. This Membership Agreement shall be construed in accordance with and governed by the laws of, and subject to the exclusive jurisdiction of the courts of, England and Wales.

Membership of The Crowdhelix Network: , on behalf of Example Membership Agreement , agrees that Example Membership Agreement shall participate as a member of The Crowdhelix Network for the duration of the Membership Period indicated above, and for any extensions to the membership duration. Crowdhelix Limited shall have the right to state on its website, social media accounts, and other publicity materials that Example Membership Agreement is a member of The Crowdhelix Network for the full duration of its membership, and is hereby granted a licence to use Example Membership Agreement’s logo for this purpose.

Abdul Rahim, on behalf of Crowdhelix Limited, grants membership of The Crowdhelix Network to Example Membership Agreement for the Membership Period indicated above (and for any extensions granted to the membership duration) once the Membership Fee has been paid in accordance with the terms of the relevant invoice (or renewal invoice, in the case of extension).

Crowdhelix Limited shall make reasonable efforts in good faith to ensure that Example Membership Agreement derives value from its membership of the platform in accordance with the benefits outlined above, for the Membership Period and for any extensions to the membership duration.

Termination by Member: Example Membership Agreement may terminate its membership with immediate effect by written request; however following such termination no amount of any Membership Fee already paid shall be refunded.

Termination by Crowdhelix Limited: If Crowdhelix Limited reasonably believes that Example Membership Agreement is acting, or will act, in a manner contrary to the legitimate interests of The Crowdhelix Network, or of any of its members, Crowdhelix Limited may terminate its membership with immediate effect by written notice.

Unless such termination was preceded by a wilfully damaging act by Example Membership Agreement, following such a termination Crowdhelix Limited shall refund a proportion of the Membership Fee to Example Membership Agreement, calculated *pro rata* for each full remaining calendar month of the current Membership Period.

Activity: , on behalf of Example Membership Agreement, understands that although Example Membership Agreement has no obligations to Crowdhelix Limited other than those listed in this Membership Agreement, proactive participation by Example Membership Agreement and its staff in the activities and platforms of The Crowdhelix Network will be necessary in order for Example Membership Agreement to derive value from its membership. Crowdhelix Limited's role in this regard shall be that of a facilitator and provider of non-binding guidance, for which no warranty or representation of any kind is made, given or implied as to its sufficiency or fitness for purpose.

Liability: Neither Example Membership Agreement nor Crowdhelix Limited shall be responsible to the other party for any indirect or consequential loss or similar damage such as, but not limited to, loss of profit, loss of revenue or loss of contracts, provided such damage was not caused by a willful act or gross negligence.

Confidentiality: Example Membership Agreement and Crowdhelix Limited agree to take all reasonable steps to ensure that information disclosed by the other party and/or any other member of The Crowdhelix Network that is marked or indicated as confidential remains confidential, and not to disclose such confidential information either directly or indirectly to any party without the written consent of the disclosing party. These obligations shall apply for a period of five (5) years from initial disclosure, but shall not apply to any disclosures required in order to comply with applicable laws or regulations or with a court or administrative order.

For the avoidance of doubt, Crowdhelix Limited is expressly unable to warrant (and has no means to procure) that any information disclosed by Example Membership Agreement to any third party or third parties to this Membership Agreement (such as, but without limitation, other members of The Crowdhelix Network) will not be disclosed and/or utilised by said party(ies). Example Membership Agreement hereby assumes full responsibility for any and all disclosures of its information to third parties to this Membership Agreement, even if such third parties may be connected to, or under a separate contract with, Crowdhelix Limited.

Data Protection: Any information supplied by Example Membership Agreement to Crowdhelix Limited, and any information (including personal data) that may be collected from its staff and other individuals associated with it, shall be held and processed in accordance with Crowdhelix Limited's current [Terms of Service, Data & Privacy Policies](#), in line with relevant legislation including the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). As set out in these policies, such information will be retained on various databases and will be used for purposes such as network, platform, and event administration. If you, or any affected individual within Example Membership Agreement, do not consent to the above policies and/or the processing of personal data, please inform us immediately. Personal data must only be directly supplied by Example Membership Agreement to Crowdhelix Limited with the express consent of the data subject(s) concerned, and under an appropriate data processing agreement or transparent joint controller arrangement.

Data subjects associated with Example Membership Agreement who supply their personal data directly to Crowdhelix Limited (e.g. when signing up to the Crowdhelix platform) will be required to confirm their own consent to the above policies, and to the processing of their personal data, in accordance with relevant legislation.

All individuals associated with Example Membership Agreement may easily opt out of any of our communications by using the tools provided within them, and may also make GDPR data subject requests by either emailing deletions@crowdhelix.com or by submitting a specific request directly within their profile page on the Crowdhelix platform.

Membership Agreement Signatures:

This Membership Agreement agreed on behalf of Example Membership Agreement

Signature & Date

This Membership Agreement agreed on behalf of Crowdhelix Limited

Abdul Rahim
Director

Signature & Date
